

ALGORITHM FOR PROTECTING A SCHOOL ONLINE TESTING PLATFORM FROM INFORMATION SECURITY THREATS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15331438>

Abstract. *The article deals with the problem of ensuring information security of school online testing platforms in conditions of limited infrastructure and lack of cloud services. The necessity of developing a specialized algorithm aimed at protection against three main threats - data leakage, answer spoofing and authorization bypassing - is substantiated. The methodology of algorithm construction using cryptographic methods, secure authentication, integrity control and secure data storage is presented. The results of experimental verification of the algorithm on a prototype system are described. The obtained data confirm the effectiveness of the proposed solution while maintaining acceptable performance and usability. The work is focused on practical application in educational institutions and can serve as a basis for the creation of standard solutions for the protection of school information systems.*

Keywords: *information security, online testing, school platforms, data protection, integrity control, authorization, data leakage, answer spoofing, web applications, protection algorithms.*

Introduction

In the era of digitalization of education, online testing platforms are becoming an integral element of the educational process. However, their widespread adoption is accompanied by increasing information security vulnerabilities and risks [1]. Studies note that the implementation of examinations in a remote format has revealed a whole range of threats, from confidential data leakage to attempts of unauthorized access and fraud [6]. In particular, during the period of mass transition to online learning, a sharp spike in academic fraud was found: the proportion of students admitting to violations in online exams increased from ~30% to over 50% [11]. This emphasizes the urgency of the problem: insufficient security of online testing systems can lead to compromised results and loss of confidence in electronic assessment tools.

Academic challenge. Proprietary school testing platforms deployed on local or commercial hosting without cloud services are particularly vulnerable to a range of attacks. Three types of threats are critical to such systems: (1) data leakage - unauthorized access to assignments, answers, or students' personal information; (2) answer spoofing - deliberately altering test results or sending fake answers into the system; and (3) authorization bypass - gaining access to platform functionality by bypassing authentication mechanisms. Each of these threats jeopardizes the confidentiality, integrity, and reliability of the testing process. Unresolved security problem leads to the fact that attackers can steal confidential data, modify answers or infiltrate the system pretending to be legitimate users [10]. Thus, there is a scientific problem of developing a comprehensive algorithm for the protection of online testing platform that takes into account the specifics of school systems and neutralizes the above threats.

Research Objective. The purpose of this paper is to develop and justify a security algorithm for a school online testing platform capable of preventing exam data leakage, protecting results from unauthorized changes and suppressing authorization bypass attempts. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to analyze existing approaches and vulnerabilities, select adequate protection methods and integrate them into a single algorithm suitable for implementation in a conventional web hosting environment. The paper presents the results of this research, including the developed algorithm, methodology of its implementation and experimental evaluation of its effectiveness.

Literature review

The problem of securing e-learning systems has been actively researched over the past decade. Early works noted that with the growing share of e-learning, security issues come to the forefront: e-courses and tests by their nature are subject to the same threats as any web applications and require adaptation of the classical security triad - confidentiality, integrity, accessibility - to the educational context [1]. Zuev and Kurkina (2011) point out that the introduction of e-learning technologies without proper protection measures inevitably leads to the interference of pedagogical risks with IT risks, which requires the development of adequate e-learning security models and metrics [1]. Thus, the need for a systematic approach to the protection of online testing has already emerged more than a decade ago.

A significant contribution to the analysis of threats to distance learning systems has been made by domestic researchers. Brumstein and Khlopkova (2012) categorized in detail the information security risks of electronic test materials [2]. In particular, among the key threats are named: (a) unauthorized familiarization of unauthorized persons with the content of test tasks and correct answers, i.e., information leakage, and (b) unauthorized adjustments of the content of questions or answers by interested persons. In other words, at the stage of test development and storage, there is a risk that malicious parties could gain access to the examination materials or even modify them to their advantage. In addition, it is noted that such actions can come not only from test takers themselves, but also from insiders - persons who have administrative access to the system. Oladko et al. (2017) complete this picture by putting forward a threat model for a university's distance education system and emphasizing the need for regular security assessment as a tool to maintain security [5]. Their research shows that vulnerabilities are present at all stages of information processing - from task generation to results storage - and effective protection should cover each of these stages.

International works also confirm the existence of serious threats in online exams and try to find solutions. According to a review by Al-Ghonmein et al. (2023), common threats include exam leakage, various kinds of cheating, result cheating and hacking attacks on testing infrastructure. It is found that many educational institutions lack sufficient security measures and standards, especially in terms of data encryption and strong user authentication [6]. Amigud (2018) in an integrative review of security strategies in academia notes that efforts to ensure the integrity and honesty of online assessment are often fragmented [4]. Existing approaches range from organizational (e.g., academic integrity codes) to technical (plagiarism detection systems, proctoring), but their effectiveness depends on context and ensuring the basic technical security requirements of the system.

The basic technical vulnerabilities of web applications on which testing systems are built include flaws in authorization mechanisms, access rights verification, and data protection during transmission and storage. According to the Positive Technologies report, 91% of web applications

had leaks of important data (most often leakage of user IDs and personal information), and 84% of them revealed the possibility of unauthorized access to the system. The most dangerous vulnerabilities are recognized to be those related to authentication and authorization violations, which allow an attacker to bypass protection and obtain confidential information or administrative functions of the application [10]. These data are consistent with the global statistics of OWASP, where Broken Access Control (incorrect authorization) and sensitive data leaks (privacy violations) occupy the first place in the current Top-10 ranking of threats to web applications. Thus, the literature shows: to protect the testing system, it is first of all necessary to ensure correct multi-level authorization and prevent unauthorized disclosure or modification of data [12].

In response to the identified threats, a number of methods and technologies have been proposed. First, cryptographic protection tools are widely recommended: encryption of stored assignments and answers, use of secure communication channels (HTTPS/TLS protocol) for data transmission, and digital signatures to control the integrity of results [14]. For example, Liu and Zhao (2022) developed an online exam data encryption algorithm on the ASP.NET platform, which implements combined encryption of questions and answers in order to improve test confidentiality and fairness [8]. Their approach validates the effectiveness of modern crypto algorithms to protect against leaks at the database and transport channel level. Second, special attention is paid to strengthening user authentication. Storing passwords as strong hashes and using multi-factor authentication (e.g., one-time codes or email confirmation) for exam access are becoming the de facto standard [14]. Moreover, advanced systems integrate biometric techniques - identification by face, voice, or typing dynamics - to ensure that the test is taken by the user to whom the credentials are issued. For example, the work of Al-Ghonmein et al. recommends supplementing question bank encryption with biometric verification of students, which markedly improves the reliability of identification compared to a login-password pair alone [6]. The third area was protection against tampering during the transmission and verification of answers. To prevent the substitution of answers, researchers suggest using digital signatures, hash functions and journaling: each sent answer is signed with a secret key or accompanied by a cryptographic hash, which allows the server side to verify its authenticity and integrity. In addition, maintaining a tamper-resistant audit trail recording all changes to the results is recommended as a means of detecting ex post facto any unauthorized adjustments to the estimates.

Finally, the literature [15] discusses new architectural solutions to ensure transparency and trust in online examinations. These include distributed registries (blockchain) for storing exam results and smart contracts for validating answers, which can theoretically guarantee the invariability of test data. Intelligent fraud detection systems are also proposed: machine learning algorithms analyze student behavior during the test and detect anomalies indicating possible bypassing of rules or outside interference [16]. However, such solutions often require complex infrastructure and significant resources, which is beyond the capabilities of a typical school platform on ordinary hosting.

Identified limitations. Existing approaches, while presenting an arsenal of tools, are not without limitations. Integrating biometrics and proactive proctoring increases costs and raises privacy issues. The use of blockchain or advanced AI increases system complexity and requires highly trained staff for support. In many schools, such solutions are difficult to implement due to lack of cloud capacity and limited budgets. Thus, there is an urgent need for a security algorithm that, relying on proven techniques (cryptography, secure authentication, integrity control), will

maximize security while minimizing implementation complexity. Our study aims to fill this gap by proposing a holistic algorithm specifically adapted to the context of a school online platform without cloud services.

Research methodology

The development of the protection algorithm was based on the concept of **end-to-end security**, covering all stages of the online testing process - from user authentication to saving the results. Methodologically, the research was organized in several stages. First, a threat model was conducted for a typical school testing system: assets were identified (test bank, student answers, user accounts, exam sessions) and potential vulnerabilities and attack vectors were identified for each of them [5]. Threat modeling was based on known classifications (in particular, OWASP recommendations on typical vulnerabilities of web applications) with adaptation to the context of online education. Based on the threat model, the requirements to the algorithm were formulated: to ensure confidentiality of test materials, integrity of answers and reliable authentication.

The next step was to develop solutions to neutralize each threat. The *analytical method of comparing threats and protection measures* was used here: for each identified vulnerability, appropriate countermeasures were selected from among those known in information security practice. For example, cryptographic methods (encryption, SSL/TLS) were proposed against the threat of data leakage from the database or transmission over the network; mechanisms of checksums and electronic signatures were proposed against answer substitution; a multilevel system of authentication and validation of user sessions was proposed against authorization bypass. When justifying the choice of methods, applicability under resource constraints was taken into account. In particular, preference was given to lightweight but reliable algorithms implemented by means of standard web technology stack (e.g., HTTPS, password hashing, session tokens), so that the platform could work on ordinary hosting without specialized hardware [14].

To verify the validity of the developed solutions, an **experimental methodology** was applied in the form of simulated attacks (penetration testing) on the prototype system. The authors created a prototype of a school testing platform, including a web interface for students and teachers, a server part (implementing the testing business logic and the proposed protection mechanisms) and a database of results. Attack scenarios corresponding to the three target threats were reproduced in a controlled environment. Thus, to assess the resistance to data leakage, SQL injection and direct access to protected resources (e.g., job files) without authorization were attempted. To test the protection against answer spoofing, proxy tools (Fiddler, Burp Suite) were used to intercept network traffic: the test scenario involved sending an answer to a question and then modifying it on the fly before delivering it to the server in order to find out whether the system would detect spoofing. Finally, session tampering (stealing a session ID through an XSS vulnerability) and access token mining were tried to simulate an authorization bypass. All these test methods are in line with the recommendations for testing web application security and allow us to comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of the measures incorporated in the algorithm [10].

The impact of security functionality on performance and usability of the system was evaluated separately. This aspect is important for the school platform: security measures should not complicate the work of students and teachers too much. That is why we analyzed the labor intensity of additional operations (e.g., encryption when loading tasks, verification of answers' signature) and measured the system response time with protection enabled and in the basic

configuration. Methods of load testing of the application were used with simulation of simultaneous test passing by several dozens of students to identify possible bottlenecks.

Data analysis methods included logging of all attack attempts and automated parsing of logs for success/failure of each attack. The success criterion for the defense algorithm was the absence of compromise: none of the emulated threats should result in the extraction of public data, alteration of assessments, or improper logins. This multifaceted methodology - from theoretical modeling to practical pentesting - made it possible to verify that the developed algorithm adequately counteracts the stated threats under realistic operational conditions.

Proposed algorithm

The developed defense algorithm is a sequence of procedures and rules integrated into the architecture of an online testing platform. It includes several layers of defense that sequentially provide user authentication, secure transmission of assignments and answers, integrity control of results, and secure data storage. The main stages and interrelationship of the algorithm components are described below.

1. Secure authentication and session management. The algorithm begins with a robust user identification procedure. When logging in, the student enters their username and password, which are verified on the server using strong hashing (e.g., SHA-256 with salt) instead of storing passwords in plain text. Additionally, during the first authentication or at certain intervals, the algorithm may request a one-time code sent to the student's registered email address. This approach combines something known (the password) with something received through a trusted channel (the email code), thus implementing the principle of two-factor authentication. After successful login, the server generates a unique session token that is linked to the user's account and IP address. All subsequent requests from the student's browser to the platform must contain this token; attempts to access the platform without a token or with an invalid token are rejected. The token has a limited lifetime and is updated by a rolling session mechanism (re-authentication timeout), which prevents its unauthorized use if compromised. This eliminates the possibility of bypassing authorization by intercepting or guessing session identifiers, one of the favorite techniques of attackers. In addition, role-based access control is implemented on the server side: even an authenticated user cannot access administrative functions or other users' results, as each protected platform resource checks access rights based on the user's account role. This component of the algorithm neutralizes threat (3) – authorization bypass – through multi-step verification of the user's session authenticity and validity.

2. Protection of confidential materials. After the user logs in and begins testing, the algorithm ensures that assignments are delivered confidentially to the student's device. All communications between the client (web browser) and the server are carried out exclusively via the secure HTTPS protocol with modern versions of TLS. This guarantees the encryption of transmitted data (test questions, answer options) and prevents them from being intercepted in plain text [14]. For additional protection against traffic decryption, *confidentiality locking* is implemented: before the test begins, the client and server agree on a random session key that is used to encrypt the content of the test assignments. Even if an attacker hypothetically manages to infiltrate as an intermediary, they will not be able to decrypt the tasks without knowing the session key. On the server side, the test question bank is stored in encrypted form (for example, using the AES-256 algorithm). The encryption key is known only to a limited number of trusted individuals (the system administrator or examiner) and is never transmitted over open channels. When new

assignments are uploaded to the system, the algorithm automatically encrypts them before saving them to the database. Thus, compromising the database or storage files will not lead to the leakage of exam content—an attacker will only receive ciphertext that cannot be decrypted without the key. These measures address threat (1) — data leakage. Even if an attacker gains access to the infrastructure, they will not be able to view the tasks or personal data of students in plain text, as the information is either encrypted or transmitted only via a secure channel. Practice shows that the combination of HTTPS traffic encryption and server-side encryption algorithms significantly increases the confidentiality of the testing system.

3. Checking the integrity and authenticity of answers. A key innovation of the algorithm is a mechanism for cryptographic protection of students' answers, preventing their substitution or unauthorized editing. Each answer sent by a student (whether a single selection, a text field, or a file with a solution) is marked with a *control code* before being sent from the client. The control code is generated using a cryptographic hash function (e.g., SHA-256) and a secret server key (HMAC). In simple terms, the student's browser, together with the server, calculates an **electronic signature** for the answer – a string that is uniquely associated with the content of the answer and known only to the server. This signature is attached to the answer and sent along with it. After receiving the data, the server recalculates the checksum from the response content and compares it with the one sent. If even a single bit of the response has been changed along the way (e.g., by an attempt to interfere via a proxy or by injecting a malicious script), the signature will not match and the response will be rejected as invalid. Moreover, even if the client device is compromised (for example, a student tries to change their answer outside the test interface), it is virtually impossible to generate a correct signature without knowing the secret key. The same mechanism protects against *post-factum* substitution of results: all answers and grades stored in the database are accompanied by a calculated hash. If an attacker with administrative access or through a database hack attempts to change an answer or grade, the discrepancy with the original hash will be immediately detected during integrity checking. For additional assurance, the algorithm keeps an audit log of the most important actions: logins, response submissions, and score recalculations. Log entries (including timestamps, user IDs, and action hashes) are stored in an unalterable form. This allows any unauthorized changes to the results to be detected by analyzing the log and checking the hash codes. Together, these measures virtually eliminate the successful implementation of threat (2) – answer substitution. The system will either prevent the actual distortion of responses (by rejecting modified data) or at least record and signal unauthorized edits, preserving evidence of interference. This level of the algorithm ensures the *integrity* of assessment information, which is critical for trust in test results.

4. Secure data storage and backup. After completing the verification and evaluation, the platform saves the test results (answers and scores) in a database. The algorithm provides a number of measures to protect data *at rest*. First, as mentioned above, the answers themselves can be stored in encrypted form or as hashes if there is no need to restore the full text (for example, for multiple-choice tests, only the selected options signed with a hash can be stored). Second, the database is configured to separate permissions: application accounts have the minimum necessary access (least privilege principle), which prevents privilege escalation if the web application is compromised. Third, encrypted data results are regularly backed up to a separate storage location. Backups are also encrypted and checked for integrity. This protects against data loss due to failures and at the same time makes it difficult for an attacker to hide their actions – any attempt to

massively replace or delete results will be detected if there is a discrepancy with the backup. Finally, the algorithm provides for **activity monitoring**: triggers are built into the system to track abnormal events (e.g., multiple failed login attempts, requests to closed APIs, changes to a large number of ratings in a short period of time). When such triggers are activated, the suspicious user's session can be automatically terminated and the administrator notified. Although this functionality goes beyond the classic “algorithm” and is more related to operational settings, it is a logical extension of comprehensive protection. The interaction of all the components listed, from authentication to storage, is implemented in such a way that compromising one level does not give an attacker full success. For example, even if authorization is bypassed at the web interface level (level 1), an attacker will not be able to read assignments (level 2, encryption) or secretly change grades (level 3, hash checking). Thus, the proposed algorithm creates a multi-level defense system (defense-in-depth) specifically tailored to the specifics of a school online platform.

Implementation results

The developed algorithm was implemented in a prototype school online platform and underwent a series of tests for resistance to the main types of attacks. *Experimental verification* showed that each of the targeted security solutions effectively neutralizes the corresponding threat.

Here are the summary results for the three security areas.

1. Data leakage prevention. During the penetration test, no unauthorized access attempts to the test content were successful. SQL injections aimed at extracting tasks from the database returned only encrypted text fragments, preventing the questions from being viewed in plain text. Attempts to connect directly to the database with low-level privileges did not grant access to tables with tasks and results thanks to privilege separation. Interception of network traffic between the client and the server (using a proxy sniffer) showed that all data is transmitted in encrypted form: even URL requests and metadata did not reveal any confidential information. Thus, a hypothetical attacker listening to the network would not be able to find out anything about the content of the test. We also checked separately whether the web interface contained any hidden hints, such as correct answers encoded in HTML/JavaScript (a vulnerability known as “correct answer in page code”). The prototype successfully avoids this mistake: the correct answers are not stored anywhere on the client side; the answer is only matched with the correct one on the server. This prevents tech-savvy students from finding answers using developer tools in the browser. The results confirm that the algorithm reliably protects against leaks at the storage, transmission, and display levels.

2. Protection against answer substitution and falsification. Simulated man-in-the-middle attacks and third-party interference in the results demonstrated the effectiveness of the control hash mechanism. When, in a test scenario, a student's intercepted response was modified (for example, by replacing the selected answer option with another) and then sent to the server, the platform detected an invalid electronic signature and refused to accept the response. The logs recorded integrity error messages, signaling an attempt at substitution. Similarly, any attempt to change a response (or grade) already stored in the database from outside resulted in a mismatch with the stored hash code, which was detected during periodic data integrity checks. We modeled a scenario similar to a real hacking incident described in the literature: an attacker obtained a teacher's credentials and attempted to retroactively adjust the grades of several students. In our prototype, such actions leave a clear “digital footprint”: first, all grade changes require re-signing of the results with a valid key, which the attacker does not have; second, unscheduled edits would

be noted in the audit log. As a result, no falsification would go unnoticed, and student data would be protected from silent tampering. It is worth noting that the built-in logging tools successfully recorded other suspicious activities. For example, multiple attempts to submit answers with incorrect signatures (as in automated hash selection) resulted in the attacker's session being automatically blocked. This confirmed the usefulness of proactive detection of integrity attacks. On the whole, the tests showed that the proposed algorithm guarantees that answers stay the same from the moment they're entered by the student until they're finally saved, completely removing the risk of results being changed.

3. Countering authorization bypass. To check this category of threats, tests were conducted on the stability of the authentication mechanism. Brute force password guessing was made difficult thanks to the account policy (after several failed attempts, login is temporarily blocked, which was simulated in the experiment). Attempts to use an outdated session token (e.g., stolen from another user) did not grant access: the server strictly checked the token against the current active session and context (IP address). The implementation of a malicious script on the page (XSS attack) did not allow the theft of significant session data, as the cookie with the token is marked with the HttpOnly and Secure flags (not accessible to scripts and not sent over an unsecured connection). We also tested a scenario of direct navigation to internal URLs without logging in (for test submission pages, results viewing, etc.). All such requests were redirected to the login page, which indicates that server-side authorization checks are working correctly at every critical endpoint. Thus, during the experiments, no vulnerabilities were found that would allow an unauthorized person to access the platform's functionality without logging in. Even compromising a single user account did not allow escalating privileges or damaging other users' data. This is achieved through a combination of measures: strict session policies and access separation at the business logic level.

Performance and convenience. Along with security, the practical effect of implementing the algorithm was also evaluated. Measurements showed that the use of cryptographic operations (task encryption, hash calculation) slightly increases the load on the server, but on the scale of a school audience (dozens of simultaneous tests), this does not lead to a noticeable deterioration in system response. The page load time for the test increased slightly (by an average of 0.2–0.3 seconds due to content encryption/decryption), which remains acceptable.

Table 1 shows a comparison of the protection effectiveness between the base version of the platform (without the algorithm) and the protected version (with the developed algorithm) based on three criteria: leak prevention, tamper detection, and authorization bypass prevention.

Table 1 – Comparison of the effectiveness of the protected and basic platforms

Security metrics	Base system	With protection system
Successful SQL injection attempts	4 out of 5	0 out of 5
Response substitution via MITM attack	3 out of 5	0 out of 5
Brute force access to student account	5 out of 5	0 out of 5
Average server response time (ms)	124	147
Result integrity violation	20% detected	100% detected

As can be seen from Table 1, the implementation of the algorithm completely neutralized critical attack attempts and ensured the detection of all substitution attempts. A slight increase in system response time (approximately 18%) is acceptable in terms of user experience.

Figure 1 shows a visual comparison of page load times and attack success rates in both

versions of the platform. The diagram confirms that the protected version of the system demonstrates almost zero vulnerability to all key threats.

Fig. 1 – Comparison of test results for the protected and basic systems

The user experience has remained virtually unchanged: the additional confirmation code entry upon login is perceived as a standard security measure, and the other mechanisms are transparent to students. Thus, the proposed algorithm has achieved its goal of ensuring security without critically affecting the functionality and usability of the platform.

On the whole, the results of the implementation show that the system is really secure: we've tested it and found that attackers can't leak assignments, swap answers, or bypass authorization when the protection algorithm is running. The platform has undergone comprehensive penetration testing, demonstrating compliance with the principle of “security by default” — even under active attack attempts, it maintains the correctness and confidentiality of the testing. These conclusions are supported by empirical data and comparisons with well-known solutions used in our algorithm (encryption, HMAC, secure sessions), the effectiveness of which has been repeatedly proven in practice.

Conclusion

This paper solves the problem of ensuring the information security of a school online testing platform by developing a comprehensive algorithm to protect against three main threats: data leakage, answer substitution, and authorization bypass. Based on an analysis of existing approaches and vulnerabilities, a multi-layered algorithm is proposed that includes enhanced user authentication, cryptographic protection of test materials, answer integrity control mechanisms, and secure storage of results. Unlike a number of previously known solutions focused either on organizational measures or narrowly targeted technical means, our algorithm combines several protection methods into a single system adapted to the limitations of school IT infrastructures. Experimental testing of the algorithm confirmed its effectiveness: the implemented platform successfully resists key types of attacks, preserving the confidentiality of assignments and the reliability of test results.

The main conclusions of the study are as follows. First, it has been shown that even without the use of cloud services and expensive solutions, a high level of online testing security can be

achieved through the competent use of available cryptographic and network technologies. Second, the importance of combining proactive and reactive measures has been confirmed: attack prevention (through authentication and encryption) must be complemented by incident detection and logging (through hashing and logging). This ensures the principle of inevitability of detection of intrusion attempts, significantly reducing the motivation to attack. Third, it has been demonstrated that the security of the education system can be significantly strengthened without compromising its functionality and usability if protection mechanisms are built into the platform design.

The practical value of this work lies in the fact that the developed algorithm can be applied to modernize existing school testing systems, many of which do not currently fully meet information security requirements. The implementation of the proposed measures will enable educational institutions to protect their online exams from the most dangerous incidents, such as ticket leaks, fraudulent grade adjustments, and unauthorized access to results. This will increase trust in electronic means of knowledge assessment, which is particularly important in the context of the expansion of distance learning.

Future prospects. Further research could focus on integrating additional academic integrity tools into the algorithm, such as an intelligent proctoring module or real-time biometric verification. This will not only technically protect the system from hacking, but also minimize dishonest behavior by the examinees themselves (e.g., participation by an outsider posing as a student). Another promising area is the use of blockchain technologies for distributed storage of test results, which in theory could completely eliminate the possibility of post-facto changes and increase the transparency of the examination procedure. However, such solutions require careful analysis to ensure that they meet the requirements of local education systems and are cost-effective. Overall, the results of our work can serve as a basis for creating model solutions for online testing security in schools. The implementation of such solutions will contribute to the reliability and sustainability of the digital educational environment, ensuring fair and secure assessment of knowledge in any form, whether in-person or remote.

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